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THE MECHANISM OF VICTIM RECOGNITION IN GEORGIAN CRIMINAL PROCEEDINGS AND ITS COMPLIANCE WITH INTERNATIONAL STANDARDS

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Abstract

Today, at the international level, significant attention is paid to crime victims' rights. Since the 20th century, various international and European organizations, such as the United Nations, the Council of Europe, and the European Union, have adopted a number of international instruments. All of them stipulate that victims should have access to the criminal justice system without any barriers. The precondition for accessing criminal proceedings is to be recognized as a victim. This paper will first analyze international and European standards regarding victims' recognition, then examine Georgian legislation and practice, and finally, conclude whether the Georgian legislation and practice comply with international and European standards.

Keywords: crime victims, recognition as a victim, criminal proceedings, international and European standards, Georgian legislation and practice.

Introduction

One of the core victim needs is to have access to justice. This need is reflected in all international legal instruments addressing victims' rights. Article 4 of The Declaration of Basic Principles of Justice for Victims of Crime and Abuse of Power sets forth that victims should be 'entitled to access to the mechanisms of justice and to prompt redress [...] [1]; Recital 9 of the EU Directive of 2012 on Establishing Minimum Standards on the Rights, Support and Protection of Victims of Crime, and Replacing Council Framework Decision 2001/220/JHA (the EU directive) emphasizes that sufficient access to justice should be provided to protect them from secondary and repeat victimisation, from intimidation and from retaliation [2]. Article 3 (1) of the Recommendation CM/Rec(2023)2 of the Committee of Ministers to member States on Rights, Services and Support for Victims of Crime (the 2023 recommendation) encourages member states to investigate barriers preventing victims' access to the criminal justice system [3].

Being recognized as a victim is a prerequisite for accessing justice and serves as the foundation for all other rights. It represents the fundamental token of treating victims with respect and dignity. Consequently, in the context of criminal procedures, a victimized person should be acknowledged as a person with its rights and standing in the criminal proceedings [4, p. 80]. This approach is laid down in all international and European legal instruments related to victims' rights. Therefore, this paper will first analyze international and European standards regarding crime victims' recognition, then examine Georgian legislation and practice, and finally, conclude whether the Georgian legislation

and practice comply with international and European standards.

International and European standards

In 1985, the Council of Europe adopted the Recommendation on the Position of the Victim in the Framework of Criminal Law and Procedure [5], and in 2000, *Brienen* and *Hoegen* conducted research on the implementation of the said recommendation in 22 European countries. One of the topics they studied was when an individual should be recognized as a victim. They discussed three models: 1. recognition from the moment they report a crime; 2. recognition from the moment they obtain a formal position and role; 3. postponing recognition until the accused has been found guilty [6, p. 30].

According to the third model, a victimized person is considered to be an alleged victim throughout the entire proceedings. This approach is related to the principle of the presumption of innocence, according to which the defendant is considered innocent until proven guilty by law. Considering the defendant as innocent is required to protect their rights and interests and to enable them to properly exercise their rights. However, the use of the 'non-victim' presumption will not put victims in a better position. Vice versa, it will adversely affect their legal standing. Therefore, this model should be declined [6, p. 30].

According to the second model, the recognition of victims should depend on their formal role, such as participation as an auxiliary prosecutor or a civil party in criminal procedures. Only after gaining this status will they be able to exercise their rights. This model leads to several problems in practice. For instance, victims

are not informed of their rights at the moment of reporting a crime. Moreover, if victims are not provided with information about their rights, it increases the risk of not obtaining the formal role in the criminal process. Consequently, *Brienen* and *Hoegen* concluded that this model as well does not fulfill the needs and interests of crime victims and should be rejected [6, p. 30].

Brienen and *Hoegen* suggest that the first model — recognizing a person as a victim from the moment they report a crime — is the best model because it ensures the highest level of protection for victims' rights and interests. Besides, it increases the likelihood of them being informed about their rights and staying updated on essential developments. This model also enhances victims' ability to properly assert their rights. It is worth noting that the recommendation of 1985 supports the same model [6, p. 30].

The same approach is enshrined in the EU directive. Specifically, Recital 19 states that 'a person should be considered a victim regardless of whether an offender is identified, apprehended, prosecuted, or convicted.' To prevent secondary victimization, the EU directive mandates that all individuals victimized by crime should be recognized as victims without difficulty and afforded the opportunity to exercise their rights [7, p.10]. Failure to recognize a person as a victim can result in secondary victimization [8, p. 105]. Furthermore, Article 3 of the EU directive requires states to ensure that victims have the right to receive information from the first contact with a competent authority. The directive emphasizes that the right to information is a precondition for victims to exercise other rights outlined in the directive. Therefore, recognizing someone as a victim from the moment the crime has been committed can ensure the enjoyment of other rights.

This principle is reiterated in the 2023 recommendation of the CoE that has been recently adopted and replaces the 2006 Recommendation on Assistance to Crime Victims. It should be noted that the 2023 recommendation was adopted because of the urgent necessity to furnish member States with guidelines and general principles aligned with the Council of Europe standards, keeping pace with international advancements [9, Background]. Under Article 2(5), a person should be considered to be a victim from the moment they were victimized, and the exercise of their rights should not depend on whether the perpetrator is identified, apprehended, prosecuted, or convicted. Currently, a number of member States link crucial victim rights, including information rights, to the victims' formal status in criminal proceedings. Their formal status may vary, such as being a party in criminal proceedings, serving as witnesses, or having other legal entitlements stipulated by national law that allow active participation. This poses a substantial obstacle to victims in accessing these rights. To enhance the breadth of rights as per the Recommendation, member States are advised to apply most rights without reliance on such a formal role. It is recommended that an individual be recognized as a victim, irrespective of whether they filed a formal complaint, but rather based on the moment they experienced a criminal offense [9, §43].

Furthermore, the literature is very clear on this matter. Generally, from the victims' point of view, the recognition procedure is considered humiliating, demonstrating mistrust toward, and disrespect for victims. It can cause much more harm than involving imaginary victims in criminal proceedings. The existence and involvement of a small portion of imaginary and self-styled victims can be tolerated and balanced at the expense of a larger number of real victims [10, pp. 21-22].

Georgian legislation and practice

Under the Georgian legislation, a person victimized by a crime is not considered to be a victim immediately after the crime has been committed. They attain a victim status only after being officially recognized as such by the prosecutor. Under Article 56(5) of the Criminal Procedure Code of Georgia (CPCG), 'if there are appropriate grounds for recognizing a person as a victim or as a legal successor of the victim, the prosecutor shall issue a decree on his/her own initiative, or upon the filing of the relevant application by that person. [...]'. Once the person is granted victim status, a prosecutor, or upon their instructions, an investigator, explains to them all the rights provided for by the CPCG. Additionally, only the person recognized as a victim can exercise the rights defined in the CPCG. Therefore, recognition as a victim is a precondition for enjoying other rights. If a person is not granted the victim status, they remain entirely excluded from criminal proceedings and cannot exercise the rights enshrined in Article 57 of the CPCG, such as the right to information, the right to review the materials of the criminal case, etc.

The mechanism of recognition as a victim should be criticized from various perspectives. First, it is inconsistent with international and European standards. Every legal instrument discussed above explicitly states that criminal justice system should be accessible for victims and the states should eliminate all barriers preventing victims' access to it. All victimized persons should be treated as victims right from the moment a crime has been committed. The mechanism of recognition as a victim violates human dignity. According to Article 1 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, 'all human beings are born free and equal in dignity and rights' [11]. Therefore, victims have the right to be treated with dignity and respect in criminal proceedings. Human dignity entails acknowledging victims as autonomous persons in criminal proceedings. The mechanism applied in Georgia risks that some victims will not be recognized as such and cannot enjoy their rights.

The phrase 'appropriate grounds' in Article 56(5) causes confusion and leads to inconsistent practices. It is unclear what is meant by 'appropriate grounds,' resulting in varied approaches used by prosecutors. This inconsistency leads to the non-recognition of many victimized individuals, leaving them excluded from criminal proceedings. Sometimes, the prosecutors recognize persons as victims several months after launching an investigation, leaving victims excluded during crucial stages [8, pp.106-108].

The Public Defender of Georgia considers this issue one of the most problematic aspects in criminal proceedings. According to the Public Defender's reports, in some cases, the victim is recognized as soon as the alleged crime occurs, but in most instances, recognition occurs after receiving expert opinions and, in some cases, only following the initiation of criminal prosecution. Consequently, year after year, numerous citizens approach the Public Defender, claiming victimization from specific criminal acts. However, the official victim status is often delayed for them, leading to a lack of information about the ongoing investigation. As per the Public Defender's recommendation, it is crucial to ensure the prompt recognition of victims at the early stage of the investigation, without unnecessary delay [12, pp. 127-128]. Additionally, critics are expressed by organizations representing victims in the criminal cases. For instance, the Georgian Young Lawyers' Association (GYLA) states that the rate of granting the victim status to those who have experienced ill-treatment is relatively low. Out of 10 cases handled by the GYLA, only two persons were recognized as victims [13, p. 6]. The Georgian Democracy Initiative (GDI) provides that victims' participation in the investigation and access to case materials constitute a significant problem. Out of 38 cases handled by the GDI only 6 persons were granted the victim status. [14, p. 27].

Despite these loopholes, some positive tendencies are noticeable. The Special Investigation Service, which investigates violent crimes and cases of ill-treatment committed by officials [15], adopted a Guideline on Familiarization with the Criminal Case Materials and Providing Information to the Victims of Ill-treatment in 2022. The document was crafted relying on recommendations and analyses of practices from the European Court of Human Rights, and the approval of the Guideline followed a process of discussion and the exchange of opinions and recommendations on the document with human rights organizations, the Office of the Public Defender, and representatives from academia. This is the first time an investigative agency allows individuals without victim status to access and review the materials of a criminal case. This guideline will be applied to cases in which law enforcement officers are accused of violence and ill-treatment [16].

Another significant achievement is visible in the work of the prosecution. In December 2022, the Council for Reviewing Complaints of Victims of Life Infringement cases was established within the General Prosecutor's Office of Georgia. It deals with cases of the violation of life that resulted in the death of a person. The purpose of the council is to hear victims' complaints and make just decisions. In this way, an effective justice system will be ensured [17].

Conclusion

Based on the comparison of the Georgian legislation and practice with international and European standards, it can be stated that the Georgian legislation and practice do not comply with international and European standards. Under Georgian legislation, crime victims do not have free access to the criminal procedures. The mechanism of victim recognition leads to

the violation of victims' dignity, causes their secondary victimization, and deprives them of the possibility to participate in criminal proceedings. Therefore, it is of paramount importance to amend the legislation and abolish the current mechanism. This amendment will have two positive outcomes: first, victims will have access to the criminal justice system without barriers, and secondly, it will lead to consistent prosecutorial practice.

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